

Assessment of Bacterial Contamination on the Hands Assessment of Poultry Butchers and Determination of Mdr Resistance Salmonella

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Background

Hands play a vital role in the prevention of infectious diseases as most of them are caused due to the transmission of microorganisms spread by contaminated hands.

Objective

The present study was conducted in Hyderabad and Jamshoro districts of Pakistan to assess the handwashing practices of poultry butchers using a questionnaire survey.

Methodology

Microbial assessment of hands of butchers was also carried out by using some standard microbiology techniques. Three hygiene indicator bacteria were targeted in this regard, namely, *Salmonella*, *Shigella*, and *E. coli*. Moreover, for *Salmonella*, antibiotic resistance was also carried out against the commonly used antibiotics.

Results

Survey results revealed that none of the slaughtering facilities had any hand washing station, clean rinsing water, soap/hand wash, or any other hand washing facility. Microbial analysis revealed that 35 (92.1%), 37 (97.3%), and 38 (100%) of hand samples were positive for *Salmonella*, *Shigella*, and *E. coli*. The results of the disc diffusion test revealed that 89.4% of isolates were resistant to ampicillin, 2.5% to azithromycin, 26.3% to gentamicin, 26% to

cefotaxime, 34.2% to erythromycin, 27% to streptomycin, and 2.6% to sulphamethoxazole. None of the isolates showed resistance to ceftazidime. Out of 35 isolates, 25 isolates were Multidrug-resistant (MDR), and one isolate (2.85%) was extremely drug-resistant (XDR).

Conclusion

The study concludes the presence of *Salmonella*, *Shigella*, and *E. coli* in poultry slaughterhouse workers. The high prevalence of *Salmonella*, *Shigella*, and *E. coli* can transfer to the meat and cause many foodborne infections in meat consumers. Moreover, the high resistant profile of *Salmonella* spp. can cause treatment failure against *Salmonella* infections.

Keywords: Hands, Hygiene, Butchers, MDR, and Antibiotics